

Nutrisystem Plans For Weight Loss

1. Nutrisystem Basic

This is the most basic meal plan which delivers three meals per day plus snacks. It doesn't allow user customization.

2. Nutrisystem Core

Nutrisystem Core allows users to customize their diet plan from over 100 different foods.

3. Nutrisystem Basic

Uniquely Yours is the most popular meal plan because of its larger variety of foods, 160 different food options.

4. Uniquely Yours Ultimate

The Uniquely Yours Ultimate plan is similar to the original Uniquely Yours but with 28 additional shakes options.

5. Diabetes plan

This plan is specifically designed for people with fluctuating blood sugar levels.

6. Vegetarian plan

This meal plan is for vegetarians who eat only plant-based foods to lose weight.

Nutrisystem Plans offers many unique plans, differentiated by structure, food preferences and cost.

Get Nutrisystem With Great Discounts